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ANNUAL REVIEW REPORTS INCLUDING GENDER EQUALITY ACTIONS & MONITORING

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Project FreeWheel “Lifecycle-reconfigurable Smart Mobility Platform to enable autonomous and cost-effective personalized solutions for social inclusion of disabled and elderly while leveraging AM technologies” (Grant Agreement number 768908) is a four year project started on October the 1st 2017. The project has the main objectives of:

- Promoting social inclusion of disabled and elderly by developing a smart mobility platform based on a reconfigurable autonomous unit to ease individual mobility in urban environment.
- Satisfying the need of customization both for the disabled and for the unit by implementing a modular reconfigurable concept based on standard low-cost modules and on ultra-customized interfaces to be produced by additive manufacturing.
- Making affordable the lifecycle cost of the above-mentioned mobility service/product by implementing an innovative business model.

The project is structured in nine work packages This report focuses on the activities already undertaken within work package (WP) 2 identifying the main results achieved and transferred to the whole project; it also documents the activities started in WP3 on FreeWheel product design and in WP9 on communication, dissemination and exploitation. A short description of activities expected within the next year for the WPs active or to be initiated is also provided.

WP2, which concluded at the end of Year One, had the main objective of identifying the design and functional requirements for FreeWheel integrated solution. The WP worked first on the alignment of the project objectives with the expectations of the end user while also aligning the project team in terms of understanding of the objectives and outcomes of the solution to be delivered. The WP issued six deliverables, of which two describing the potential users and their experience of the solution and two describing the technical and service objectives and the road map for the project to achieve lasting social impact. The latter were then translated into requirements and features of the solution. The set of objectives – key results – requirement and features provide the inputs for an online interactive platform supporting the cocreation of the FreeWheel solution throughout the project.

WP3 focuses on the design of the FreeWheel mobility mechatronic solution consisting of the active module (the motor), the connector with the wheel chair and the motion system (the wheels and support structure) which will be customized on the specific operating environment. WP3 activities focused on the review of available electric motors and sensors and the current state of the art with respect to electric wheelchair applications and alternative small scale mobility solutions. It also set up the Lifecycle Engineering Platform, the online tool for configuring and reconfiguring FreeWheel units, customizing the modules of the wheelchair and managing the engineering, manufacturing, and configuration. The activities of WP3 are continuing on regulatory and standardisation aspects, on the validation of the specific elements of the solution and on the evaluation of the features derived from WP2.

WP9 focuses on the dissemination and exploitation of FreeWheel project results. It focused mainly on scientific dissemination with the definition of a plan for the identification of conferences and publishing opportunities, including journals, white papers and data sets for the Open Repository. Standardisation committees of relevance and industrial platforms to be contacted have also been identified.

Other project activities included a project team visit to both sites identified for the demonstration activities at the end of the project and some communication activities in Italy. A gender equality monitoring activity was undertaken, which highlighted that, since the start project FreeWheel has had a very good gender balance, achieving nearly a 50:50 split already at the end of Year One.

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Introduction

Project FreeWheel “Lifecycle-reconfigurable Smart Mobility Platform to enable autonomous and cost-effective personalized solutions for social inclusion of disabled and elderly while leveraging AM technologies” (Grant Agreement number 768908) is a four year project started on October the 1st 2017 funded by the Horizon 2020 programme under the call Factory of the Future 2017 - topic 10 “New technologies and life cycle management for reconfigurable and reusable customised products”.

FreeWheel general objectives are to:

- Promote social inclusion of disabled and elderly **by developing a smart mobility platform** based on a **reconfigurable autonomous unit** to ease individual mobility in urban environment. The versatility of FreeWheel solution allows compensating for the presence of physical barriers, helping to extend the degree of access to contexts and autonomy of the person with disability in an increasing number of environments.
- Satisfy the **need of customization** both for the disabled and for the unit by implementing a **modular reconfigurable concept based on standard low-cost modules and on ultra-customized interfaces** to be **produced by additive manufacturing**. Modularity, by using low cost standard modules (engine, gears, control unit, HMI, etc.) and highly customized interface (body to unit, engine to unit, unit to infrastructure, etc.); Reconfigurability, by allowing an ease re-use of standard modules in different products (e.g. same electrification module in different unit fleets, differently customized to the surrounding environment);
- Make **affordable** the **lifecycle cost** of the above-mentioned mobility service/product by implementing an innovative business model that
 1. offers the mobility as a service separating the use from the ownership of the units,
 2. leverages manufacturing dematerialization to reduce lead time and investment cost, in particular Additive Manufacturing technologies to reduce the cost of person-to-unit personalization and unit-to-infrastructure customization,
 3. shares investment, cost and revenues all along the relevant stakeholders along the mobility value chain: disabled, urban centre, infrastructure owners, vehicle integrators, service providers, components suppliers, Additive Manufacturing centres. An affordable synergetic investment in the infrastructure is necessary to make simple and affordable the positioning and navigation system (WP6, value chain),
 4. leverages product reconfigurability, achieved thanks to product modularity, to cover large production volumes through the sum of small batches of highly customised products whose configuration is supported by a co-engineering digital platform involving players belonging to the entire supply chain,
 5. extends the lifecycle of product by re-use, re-manufacturing and possible upgrade of components.

The project is implemented by a Consortium of eleven organisations including SMEs, Research Centres, Public Entities, NGOs from Italy, Switzerland, Spain, Greece and the UK.

The work is structured in nine work packages illustrated below, with links to the objectives of the project.

Figure 1 FreeWheel work packages and links with project objectives

The first year of the project concluded with the completion of work package 2, which had started at month 1 of the project while work package 3 and 9 started mid-year and are continuing throughout Year 2 at least. All the other work packages are starting within Year 2 of the project with the exception of WP8 that is focusing on the demonstration of the proposed solution, which will start at the beginning of Year 3 of the project.

This report focuses on the activities already undertaken within work package (WP) 2 identifying the main results achieved and transferred to the whole project; it also documents the activities started in WP3 on FreeWheel product design and in WP9 on communication, dissemination and exploitation. A short description of activities expected within the next year for the WPs active or to be initiated is also provided.

Work Package 1: Project Management

This WP covers the administrative and coordination aspects of the project. A separate, confidential, administrative and financial report on these aspects has been produced (Deliverable D1.4) for the European Commission.

Work Package 2: Human centred requirements and objectives

OBJECTIVES

Work package 2 has had the main objective of identifying the design and functional requirements for FreeWheel integrated solution.

More specifically, the objectives of the WP have been as follows:

- definition of users' archetypes constituting the needs, behaviours, and characteristics of prospect clients;
- detection of the major situational-handicaps;
- mapping of the current experience journey for the pilot project's contexts;
- designing the new customers' experiences according to the FreeWheel concept;
- definition of design objectives for: (1) technical, (2) service. (3) social point-of-view with the related KPIs;
- definition of technical requirements list and service requirement list.

The WP was led by Keen Bull and saw the contribution of all project partners.

ACTIVITIES

Starting in earnest from the first month, the work package worked on two main areas:

- the alignment of the team in terms of understanding of the objectives and outcomes of the solution to be delivered
- the alignment of the project objectives with the expectations of the end users.

The alignment of the team was undertaken through a workshop held at the First General Assembly with the collection of "stories", i.e. statements of intent written as meaningful people outcomes. Structured to contain certain key elements (*who*, what and the **wow**, the innovative factor), the stories allowed the whole FreeWheel consortium to explore breakthrough ideas related to the project. A generic and a FreeWheel specific examples are provided below:

GENERIC EXAMPLE: *A firefighter chief can assemble a response team in under 10 minutes without management involvement*

FREEWHEEL EXAMPLE: *A client can book and rent the module with voice commands*

The stories were collected in an online repository and further explored with the single proposers before regrouping into categories related to the aspects of the FreeWheel solution under consideration, e.g.: functionalities of the app service to the user, features of the hardware, impact on the supply chain.

The alignment of the project objectives with the end users (called "sponsors") started with a key activity of clarification of the concept of "disability" functional also to define the end users of the project. FreeWheel solution addresses mainly disability related to a limitation of the ability to move; however, as this limitation might be the result of many different injuries or illnesses, the FreeWheel solution will only be able to address the needs of certain categories of motor disability, as illustrated in Deliverable D2.2 – Behavioural archetypes. The insight of the end user partner Genny Angels was key

in enabling the project team to clarify this important concept hence to proceed to address the definition of the users' archetype through the identification of a panel of sponsors to be interviewed. Some six sponsors with different categories of disability were asked face to face questions. The analysis of such interviews enabled the definition of four behavioural archetypes where different users' requirements relevant for the FreeWheel solution were highlighted (Deliverable D2.2 – Behavioural archetypes). The point of view of the sponsors was also used to trace the Experience Maps, i.e. the journey of a user as it interacts with the FreeWheel solution, from downloading the app and subscribing to the service through booking and using the mobility hardware solution to the payment of the service and the obtainment of the receipt. This conceptual journey adapted to the two environments to be demonstrated – the indoor mall and an outdoor archaeological attraction – has allowed the team to identify potential pain points to avoid and also features required to ensure the experience of the user runs as smoothly as possible (Deliverable D2.1 – FreeWheel experience map).

A review of the technical and service objectives, presented in the FreeWheel proposal, was undertaken with key partners to verify their validity and any additional specification as gathered from the previous exercises and the initial work from WP3. The review also used the MECE framework (“Mutually Exclusive and Collectively Exhaustive”) to eliminate overlapping objectives and ensuring clarity through applying the SMART framework, (Specific, Measurable, Agreed between all the partners, Realistic and Time-based). (Deliverable D2.3 Technical and Service Objectives and key results + KPIs). With respect to the social impact, Keen Bull guided the project partners through a number of exercises to build the Theory of Change model (deliverable D2.4 Theory of Change Logic model), i.e. a conceptual roadmap describing how the project is expected to achieve its long-lasting impacts.

All the objectives identified within D2.2, D2.3 and D2.4 were then analysed to identify the high level objectives not yet explicated into key results (mainly those from the Experience map and the Theory of Change) and to assign responsibilities for each within the project consortium (Deliverable D2.5 - Technical and service requirements). These are the basis for defining the requirements deriving from the key results and translating those into features of the FreeWheel solution. The matrix derived is a “live” document requiring updating throughout the project, with a Change Leadership Board instituted to ensure this. Members of the Change Leadership Board are named within D2.5 and include representatives from IRIS srl, SUPSI, Genny Angels, Keen Bull and MCH Tronics.

The above set of objectives – key results – requirement and features provide the inputs for Deliverable D2.6 -Creating a shared and always available service repository, which is an online interactive platform supporting the cocreation of the FreeWheel solution throughout the project.

Work Package 3 FreeWheel product design

OBJECTIVES

WP3 focuses on the design of the FreeWheel mobility mechatronic solution consisting of the active module (the motor), the connector with the wheel chair and the motion system (the wheels and support structure) which will be customized on the specific operating environment. The product design practice will also make use of data collection and synthesis coming from advanced sensing system nested in the FreeWheel solution.

Summarising all the defined and most important features, the FreeWheel solution has to be at least:

- A completely autonomous vehicle
- Equipped with a complete set of proximity sensors or a visual system for the object detection and obstacle avoidance
- Lightweight and not bulky/uncomfortable device
- Able to move in indoor and outdoor ground conditions
- Equipped by several driving control solutions like a Joystick, a smartphone app or a touchscreen customized in function of the necessities
- Other HMI interfaces

MCH Tronics leads this WP still ongoing, with major contributions from SUPSI, LMS and KUMO.

ACTIVITIES

WP3 activities focused on the review of:

- the current state of the art with respect to electric wheelchair applications and other alternative small scale mobility solutions (e.g. mobile platforms for moving small loads)
- electric motors and available sensors

and on the set up of the Lifecycle Engineering Platform.

Electric wheelchair applications

The WP identified a number of solutions for the electrification of the wheelchairs, which have been found to be either add ons [Figure 2] - like NINO ONE and Smart Drive Mx1- or complete wheelchair solutions - like NINO Robotics and Genny mobility.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 1 (a) NINO ONE Robotics; (b) NINO Robotics; (c) e-fix E36; (d) Rio Firefly; (e) Smart drive Mx1 (f) SBA029 Sherpa KSP

Pros and Cons of all solutions were analysed also with the help of Genny Angels and of customers' videos to identify features/functionalities to avoid or to take into account when designing the FreeWheel solution. For instance, the team learned how the front wheels constitute an issue as they do not perform well on irregular terrain and even constitute a dangerous features when there are gaps in the road; furthermore, solutions that tend to lift such wheels need to make sure the balance of the wheelchair is maintained at all times.

Mobile Robots analysis

A second state of the art analysis focused the attention on the Autonomous Guided Vehicles (AGV) and the Mobile Robot Platforms (MRP) as potential basis for the mobility solution, to gather information on the following characteristics:

- Payload, total weight, dimension, max incline and ground clearance
- Traction system, motors type, battery type and max speed
- Communications types, Software and Hardware characteristics and customizing level
- Indoor and outdoor application

The main findings were as follows:

- 1) The AGV [Figure 3] is one of the material handling methods that has been widely used in most industry nowadays. They are able to follow markers or wires in the floor or to exploit vision, magnet or laser systems for the navigation. The following table depicts a restricted list of AGVs on the market.

Fig. 2 (a) RB-2 base Robotnik; (b) Vector Stanley Robotics; (c) Flex omni Stanley Innovation; (d) Ridgeback Clear Path; (e) MPO- 700 Neobptix and (f) Model DC - 10.

From an initial examination, it appears that most of them are characterized by a high payload values, which is relevant for the objectives of the FreeWheel solution. However, they have ground clearance values very small, a strong disadvantage as a vehicle with a low ground clearance value does not allow to travel on all the possible terrains, which is a requirement for the FreeWheel solution.

Another important quality regards the total weight, FreeWheel has to be as lighter as possible in order to guarantee the motion also when the device is turned off. The AGVs from this point of view are not close to the final solution.

Finally, with respect to the maximum incline, the AGVs are not suitable for big slopes. Usually they can travel up to 5 degrees. Table. 3 below summarises the findings of the analysis.

Model	Payload (Kg)	Weight (Kg)	Size (m)	GC (mm)	OT (hrs)	CT (hrs)	MI (°)	MS (km/h)
RB-2 base Robotnik	200	95	0.74x0.54x0.36	-	10-20	-	-	6.12
Vector Stanley Robotics	124	45.4	0.67x0.50x0.31	25.4	5	2-5	5	7.2
Flex omni Innovation	450	128	1.58x0.79x0.4	144	Up to 24	2 - 3	5	7.92
Ridgeback Clear Path	100	135	0.96x0.79x0.30	-	15	8	-	3.96
MPO- 700 Neobptix	400	120	0.74x0.51x0.35	23	5	4	-	3.4
Model DC - 10	907.18	158.7	1.194x0.51x0.38	-	8	-	-	3.66

Table. 1 GC Ground Clearance, OT Operating Time, CT Charging time, MI Max Incline, MS Max Speed

- The Mobile Robot Platforms (MRPs) [Figure 4], instead, have the capability to move around in their environment and not in a fixed physical location. They are capable of navigating in an uncontrolled environment without any physical devices.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(h)

(i)

Fig. 3 (a) Husky ClearPath; (b) RMP440 SE Segway; (c) Innok Heros; (d) Warthog ClearPath; (e) Seekur; (f) Summit XL Robotnik; (g) Guardian Robotnik; (h) RMP440 LE Segway and (i) Super Mega Bot.

The following table depicts a restricted list of MRPs on the market.

Model	Payload (Kg)	Weight (Kg)	Size (m)	GC (mm)	OT (hrs)	CT (hrs)	MI (°)	MS (km/h)
Husky ClearPath	75	50	0.99x0.67x0.39	130	3	4	45	3.6
RMP440 SE Segway	180	106	1.11x0.84x0.61	272	Up to 24	2-3	30	28.8
Innok Heros	400	140	1.70x1.20x0.50	195	8	3-5	45	20
Warthog ClearPath	272	280	1.52x1.38x0.83	254	6	8	35/45	18
Seekur	70	300	1.34x1.20x0.96	180	8	8	35	6.48
Summit XL Robotnik	130	90	0.70x0.52x0.42	163	10	-	30	10.8
Guardian Robotnik	100	120	1.13x0.75x0.55	104	6	-	45	4.5
RMP440 LE Segway	180	120	1.11x0.84x0.53	110	Up to 24	2-3	30	28.8
Super Mega Bot	113	100	0.84x0.84x0.41	140	1.2	-	30	24.4

Table. 2 GC Ground Clearance, OT Operating Time, CT Charging time, MI Max Incline, MS Max Speed

From an initial examination, it appears that most of them are characterized by an appropriate value of ground clearance, which is a strong advantage since the FreeWheel solution has to be able to move in indoor and outdoor contests. Moreover, the wheel types suggest a large potential of these robots in terms of suitable terrain, ride comfort etc. With regards to the payloads, they can be classified in function of the dimensions and total weight. Comparing the payloads

of those MRPs with similar characteristics it is possible to observe that they can be exploited for carrying people or tow them around.

Regarding the communication features, most of the AGVs and MRPs devices are equipped by USB ports, Ethernet, Wi-Fi, CAN bus and Bluetooth technologies.

Electric Motors analysis

WP3 analysed the electric motors, particularly those used for mobility, such as the electric bicycle. The e-bike is a bicycle with an integrated electric motor which can be used for propulsion. Many kinds of e-bikes are available worldwide, from e-bikes that only have a small motor to assist the ride's pedal-power to somewhat more powerful e-bikes which tend to be closer to motorcycle style functionality. E-bikes use rechargeable batteries and the lighter varieties can travel to 25 to 32 km/h depending on the laws of the country in which they are sold.

Some similarities with the proposed FreeWheel solution were found. Indeed, the motors offered by this type of application are super flat and light, at the same time they are very powerful and able to supply very high torque values in order to support the weight of the cyclist. Thinking about the usual wheelchairs use, a smooth acceleration and a trajectory is desired. This is why the attention is focused on the study of this devices.

In particular two main brands were selected for further analysis, Bikee Bike motors and the most common Bafang motors.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4 (a) Bafang electric motor Kit; (b) Bikee Bike electric motor Kit

Model analysis and Motor housing

With regards to the mechanical parts of the solution, standard wheelchairs were investigated, with the support of Genny Angels. The following images depict the two available models.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5 Wheelchairs provided by Genny, (a) footrest with two legs on the left and (b) footrest with one leg on the right
The wheelchairs were used to draw their CAD models, as seen below.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6 Wheelchair images (a) Vs CAD representation (b)

Once ready, the CADs are useful for initial analyses, in order to define which is the most suitable configuration for the FreeWheel solution. In the mean time, a sizing procedure is carried out so as to study which forces, torques and moments are acting on the wheelchair during the normal use. With the obtained results it is possible to understand which motors are suitable for the FreeWheel solution and where arrange them in order to exploits their potentialities and performances.

Microcontrollers, sensors and vision systems

WP3 considered the available choice of microcontrollers able to support different important components, different sensors and visual systems useful for the object detection. With this objective, several boards have been investigated with a preferred board identified in the LattePanda Alpha system.

(a) (b) (c) (d)
Fig. 7 (a) Raspberry PI ZERO W; (b) Texas Instruments LAUNCHXL-F28379D; (c) Arduino MEGA 2560 REV3; (d) LattePanda Alpha

Regarding the sensors, LCD screens, Joysticks and vision systems, it is possible to observe different selected models in the following images. All of them are under investigation in order to understand which are the most suitable devices for FreeWheel solution.

(a) (b) (c) (d) (e) (f)
Fig. 8 (a) OPT8241-CDK- Sensor evaluation model from TI; (b) Intel RealSense Depth Camera D435i; (c) Raspberry PI Touch Display; (d) Adafruit 4.3" Display Touch Screen for Arduino Mega board; (e) Joystick for Wheelchair; (f) 3d Smart Joystick with Bluetooth connection.

The above elements constitute the backbone of the FreeWheel software part, which includes the control of the motors but also all the sensing system interacting with the motion control but also delivering safety and comfort features for the user of the solution (e.g. balance, obstacle recognition and avoidance, autonomous driving, module localisation etc).

Lifecycle engineering design

KUMO Technologies is structuring the platform for configuring and reconfiguring FreeWheel units, customizing the modules of the wheelchair and managing the engineering, manufacturing, and configuration. The platform has been planned to constitute the framework integrating the chain that will be shared by all the players in the manufacturing workflow, according to the following ideal steps:

- First step: translate the user requirement into an editable 3D CAD file of the wheelchair and rely upon a library of all modules and sub-systems composing the FreeWheel solution
- Second step: the OEM can start the personalization process in the Lifecycle Engineering Platform-CAD development module, thus customizing the components of the assembly to fit the physical and functional characteristics of the user as well as the environmental operating context
- Third step: Once the customization is completed, the Co-Engineering process will start. The suppliers of the components will be involved in the design process by starting from the shared CAD prototype version.

The Lifecycle Engineering Platform is currently live and includes one of the wheelchairs' CAD acquired within the WP3 showcasing some of the features planned, i.e. the use of standard engineering files (.stp and .igs) and their visualisation as a system and as tree of components. Users can access the platform and upload/download models for exchanging information.

ACTIVITIES ALREADY PLANNED FOR THE NEXT PERIOD

The activities are continuing with the investigation of relevant EU Directives and international standards applicable to medical devices such as wheelchairs, as they cover also electrified vehicles. Furthermore, initial tests are to be undertaken to evaluate a rear wheel direct drive solution. The sensors to be implemented within the solution are also under investigation: from their selection will derive the definition of the communication protocols and a campaign of testing.

The conclusion of WP2 has made available a full set of requirements including those relevant to the product design, and such requirements need to be reviewed for incorporation as features of the hardware and software solution. A full design of the solution (motor, batteries, connectors, sensors and electronics) will therefore start.

Work Package 9 FreeWheel Dissemination and exploitation

OBJECTIVES

This work package has the objectives of:

- Ensuring proper scientific and industrial dissemination of the project achieved results.
- Developing and updating plans for exploitation in the EU smart mobility applications based on reconfigurable products and AM based technologies.
- Assisting the establishment of business interest groups as possible channels for the implementation of exploitation plans.

ACTIVITIES

WP9 focused mainly on scientific dissemination with the definition of a plan for the identification of conferences and publishing opportunities, including journals, white papers and data sets for the Open Repository. Standardisation committees of relevance and industrial platforms to be contacted have also been identified. A dissemination plan is shortly to be published as Deliverable D9.1 – Scientific dissemination and industrial promotion plan. This is the first of the plans, to be updated annually.

Furthermore, some exploitation analysis was undertaken by partners IAM and Third party Lazzerini, who specialises in development of seats and furnishing of public transport vehicles in Europe and US. An opportunity was identified to extend the FreeWheel solution also to complement the furnishing of the space reserved for wheelchairs on buses and similar, as the anchoring of the wheelchair to the structure is done through some straps and belts. The potential for developing an attachment that could ensure a safe anchoring of the wheelchairs to the bus structure is to be further explored.

Other FreeWheel activities undertaken during Year One

- FreeWheel takes part in the Open Data pilot, hence a Data Management Plan and a Open Research Data Repository have been drafted and identified respectively in the eponymous Deliverable D1.9 and D1.10. LMS and IRIS are working together with the partners for identifying the data produced within the different tasks that are not confidential or sensitive and therefore can be uploaded onto the Open Data repository to be made available to the research community.
- Some communication activities have also been undertaken within this project, so to ensure awareness raising of the general public. They have included :
 - The set up of the project's website, which also hosts some news about the project event and all the public deliverables. A twitter account is to be soon set up to raise awareness of the project even further.
 - The participation with a presentation of the project to an event in Fontanellato, Italy during the celebrations for the town obtaining the Bandiera Lilla in recognition of the high degree of accessibility for people with motor disabilities;
 - The joined sponsorship of a vehicle specifically modified to transport people on wheelchairs and used by the Municipality local to IRIS srl to offer a service to young disabled people and their families: school run, medical visits, extracurricular activities. The name of the project and a QR code pointing to the FreeWheel website feature on the vehicle itself.
- During the first General Assembly held in IRIS, Turin, the team paid a visit to the candidate indoor demosite, a mall located in Beinasco near Turin: the team met with the Mall Director, who is the reference point for the activities related to the demo
- During the second General Assembly held in Patras and hosted by LMS, the team visited the outdoor demosite, the Patras Castle managed by partner Eforate of Antiquities of Achaia. This visit allowed the team to see first-hand the challenges of the site and to start discussing some details such as the positioning of the rack, the possible FreeWheel service route and the works required to enable that.

Activities to be started or just started in other Work Packages

WP4: FREEWHEEL SERVICE AND DIGITAL POINTS DESIGN

This work package deals with the design of the service and how the users interact with it, from subscribing to the service to accessing the module to closing the rental. The results from WP2, in particular but not only the Experience mapping, are used to define what the service should deliver and how. Keen Bull will be leading this WP that will see the contributions of most partners and will be strictly linked with WP3.

WP5: FREEWHEEL PROCESS DESIGN

Objective of this WP is the design of the manufacturing process by

- selecting the best set of technologies to be employed
- defining the process parameters and precedence constraints, to be sequenced to create a process chain that optimises e.g. productivity, energy, efficiency and accuracy.

The WP is led by IRIS with main contributions from SUPSI, LMS, Morphica and IAM.

Some activities were started with an identification of the 3D printing capabilities of Morphica, both in terms of equipment and materials: some tests are to be started by Morphica to qualify the process parameters with respect to the performance of the different material as printed.

WP6: FREEWHEEL PRODUCTION INFRASTRUCTURE

This WP has the following objectives:

- The customization of the mechatronic equipment to accomplish the production KPIs covering stand-alone resources, devices and systems to support metal and plastic based AM technologies both laser assisted and not.
- The design of the sensing system for process and equipment monitoring.
- The development of the automation and communication platforms to ensure the control, coordination, synchronization and supervision of the entire production infrastructure.

The manufacturing phase supporting the creation of the various modules composing the FreeWheel solution will cover a number of different milestones starting from the identification of the mechatronic equipment implemented technologies and process chains resulting from WP5, to the integration of the sensing device and the development of the automation infrastructure.

The WP is led by SUPSI with contributions from MCH, IRIS and LMS mostly.

Activities on this WP started earlier than planned on the sensing system task led by MCH in order to select and design the architecture of the sensing system used by the Direct Energy Deposition modules. Activities in progress are focusing on the positioning of photodiodes, pyrometers and CMOS inside the deposition head and, at the same time, their integration in the optic chain with the objective to monitor the additive and subtracting process quality, by monitoring the laser beam and the powder ejection.

All other activities within the WP will start from Month 13 at the earliest.

WP7 and WP8 will start in Year 3.

Gender equality actions

The gender equality actions within project FreeWheel can be seen both at management and participation level and also with respect to the work undertaken, specifically in terms of the expected outputs of the project.

With respect to the management and coordination, project FreeWheel has a Steering Committee composed by four members of the consortium covering the following roles:

- Project Coordinator (PC);
- Scientific and Industrial Quality Coordinator (SIQC);
- Industrial coordinator (IC);
- Scientific and Technical Coordinator (STC).

The Steering Committee interacts with a Scientific and Technical Committee composed by the Work Package Leaders.

Named representatives within the Steering Committee include a female in charge of scientific and technical coordination, who is also the Work Package Leader for WP6. Hence, nominally the project's highest-level decision making body and the representation of the technical implementation have both a 25% female representation.

Furthermore, the Project Coordinator is assisted in his management role and for administrative issues by two different female members of staff, ensuring a good female representation in the coordination team also.

Overall project participation, with respect to members of staff implementing the action, is described in the following section.

Gender had not been identified as a specificity of the objectives and outcome of the work of project FreeWheel, as FreeWheel solution addresses the needs of people with temporary or permanent severe mobility limitation whatever the gender. With respect to the definition of the users requirements, the sponsors interviewed were half male and half female to ensure also a balanced archetype definition. Whether or not there will be a gender predominance within the users of the solution because of the reduction of the physical effort required by moving a wheelchair around, this might only be captured at the end of the demonstration.

Gender equality monitoring

In Article 33 - GENDER EQUALITY, section 33.1 Obligation to aim for gender equality, the Grant Agreement recites that "The beneficiary must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action. It must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level."

Table. 3 below shows the composition of the team working for the FreeWheel project within each of the beneficiaries and in total within the Consortium.

Some 13 female and 16 male started working on the project while after Year One the number of female increased of 38% while the male contingent of the 23% only. The gender balance for the start of the project was therefore 45% female and 55% male at the beginning of the project, improving to 49% female and 51% male at the end of Year One.

With respect to team composition, since the start project FreeWheel has had a very good gender balance, achieving nearly a 50:50 split already at the end of Year One.

Beneficiaries	1 st October 2017		1 st October 2018	
	Number of female in the Freewheel team	Number of male in the FreeWheel team	Number of female in the Freewheel team	Number of male in the FreeWheel team
1 - IRIS SRL	4	1	4	1
2 - MORPHICA SOCIETA A RESPONSABILITA LIMITATA SEMPLIFICATA A SOCIO UNICO	1	1	1	2
3 - KEEN BULL SAGL	1	2	2	3
4 - MCH-TRONICS SAGL	1	2	1	2
5 - KUMO TECHNOLOGIES SL	0	1	1	1
6 - INNOVAZIONE AUTOMOTIVE E METALMECCANICA SCARL	1	0	1	0
6a - LAZZERINI	1	1	1	1
7 - GENNY ANGELS	0	2	1	2
8 - SCUOLA UNIVERSITARIA PROFESSIONALE DELLA SVIZZERA ITALIANA	2	1	2	4
9 - PANEPISTIMIO PATRON - LMS	0	2	1	5
10 - NETWORK SOCIETY RESEARCH LTD	0	1	0	1
11 - EPHORATE OF ANTIQUITIES OF ACHAIA	2	1	3	1
WHOLE CONSORTIUM	13	16	18	19

Table. 3 Gender composition of FreeWheel team at the start of the project and after Year One

Conclusions

The first year of project FreeWheel concluded with the completion of Work package 2, which had started at month 1 of the project while work package 3 and 9 started mid-year and are continuing throughout Year 2 at least. All the other work packages are starting within Year 2 of the project with the exception of WP8 that is focusing on the demonstration of the proposed solution, which will start at the beginning of Year 3 of the project.

WP2 was successful in aligning the project objectives with the end users' needs by defining first of all the category of disability FreeWheel solution will be targeting and then defining behavioural archetypes and the likely experience the FreeWheel client would have in using the solution in two typical environments of application, an outdoor tourist-cultural attraction and an indoor mall. In parallel, the team was aligned with respect to the project technical objectives while a study on the roadmap to achieve long lasting social impact contributed to define the picture of objectives and key results for the project. This co-creation approach allowed the set up of a clear chain of objectives – key results – requirements and features that are cascading down to work package 3, which deals with the design of the Hardware part of the FreeWheel solution, and to WP4, which deals with software aspects.

With the hardware solution taking shape, activities on the process design and the production infrastructure are well set to start (WP5 and WP6). At the same time, dissemination of the first project results can start, while plans for publicising the engineering results are being drafted (WP9). In the meantime, communication activities to raise awareness of the project are continuing through the website, and a Twitter account will soon be activated.